

CREATING INFLUENTIAL LEADERSHIP WITH THE HELP OF CREATIVITY AND INNOVATION

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ABSTRACT

In today's rapidly evolving business landscape, organizations must cultivate a culture of innovation to maintain a competitive edge. However, fostering creativity within a hierarchical and efficient business environment can be challenging. Nonetheless, leaders play a crucial role in inspiring and implementing strategies that promote creativity. Effective leadership acts as a catalyst for organizational creativity, imagination, innovation, and advancement. Leaders must create a climate open to renewal and cultivate an environment encouraging growth, innovation, and creativity to achieve a continuous innovation cycle. The ability of leaders to embrace and manage diversity while creating an efficient leadership structure that monitors the innovation process is essential for the success of organizational creativity. The strategic function of leadership in business innovation is examined in this study. It asserts that while innovation, technology, strategy, culture, and management tools are essential for productivity, the key factors influencing organizational success are creativity and innovation. The paper discusses creating a sustainable framework that encourages creative behavior and innovative practices. Various aspects of innovation strategy are analyzed, and the paper concludes by documenting the outcomes and providing recommendations for fostering innovation in other companies.

Keywords: Creativity, Innovation, Leader, Leadership, Sustainable Organizations

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INTRODUCTION

The present organizations mostly employ a noteworthy part of the general processes in operation, marketing, finance, and human resource development. The models many organizations have used to inform their earlier judgments must be revised for success, accomplishment, and effectiveness in the 21st-century commercial environment. These organizations differentiate themselves by specific strategies that ensure quality and a strong organizational structure that helps them grow. According to Holzmann and Golan (2016), innovation, entrepreneurship, and creativity are a result of being occasionally associated with pre-planned, standardized, and organized enterprises. However, if these characteristics are closely linked, the organization might attain an additional highly focused position in the business world.

This test is much easier to succeed when managing traditional organizations that have mastered business and organizational growth strategies. Even though the primary goal of those strategies is to produce superior quality, they need a thorough understanding of creativity, innovation, and company entrepreneurship. There is no proven approach to fostering creativity and innovation that can be immediately connected and sustained over time, even though managers today know the favorable association between innovation and corporate success (Teece, 2010). The belief that every single employee is a valued provider and that the outcomes produced by the "organizational crowd" (Osterloh & Frey, 2000) are superior to those produced by a group of professionals is the inspiration behind the improvement of innovation.

The predicament in those sectors has changed since the processes and environment were either slow or stable (Nadler & Tushman, 1997). Work forms are evolving in many areas far more quickly than in the past as organizations battle with the issues of rapidly changing technology, globalization, vulnerability, randomness, and volatility (Jamali et al., 2006). They used to be able to aim for long-term success despite failures or resistance to growth due to infrastructure constraints on the market, brand, or innovation. But given that the environment is unpredictable, a lot of these organizations need to continue to improve. To stay competitive and aggressive, they need to be creative and innovative all the time. It, therefore, shows the organizations that to deal with their innovative forms; one should notice and acknowledge the creativity and leadership present there. This organizational plan will give the organizations the tools they need to create restoration-friendly conditions, create an innovative organizational culture, and increase their organizational diversity, all of which will help them remain competitive.

In this article, we demonstrate a straightforward strategy to apply that provides a comprehensive answer to the operational and inter-organizational procedures intended to support creativity. We seek to evaluate the literature on creativity and innovation, discuss how they contribute to corporate success, particularly in the industrial setting, and present an integrated structure for both. The role and types of leadership in the innovative process are then attempted to be examined, and we conclude by looking at how leaders foster creativity and innovation. We conclude the report with closing remarks, observations on the limitations of the research, and recommendations for subsequent tests.

BACKGROUND

Many different contexts have considered how creativity and innovation affect organizational success, leading to the conclusion that social factors and assisting organizational processes weigh heavily among all the influencing factors (Heunks, 1998; Rosenbusch et al., 2011; Laforet & Tann, 2006; West & Sacramento, 2012). Although creativity and innovation are seen as essential for success and advancement and are applied consistently, they differ in logic and execution. The process of creativity involves the expression of original ideas or concepts. It oversees the development of unique, unconventional, and novel ideas that can be expressed in various ways. Innovations in creativity are typically expressed through a unique experience that may be observed, noticed, touched or tasted.

Furthermore, innovation involves integrating change into an existing framework to make a new notion plausible and significant. Innovation is how we develop better methods of carrying out a task. It could allude to subtle or significant product, service, or behavior changes.

In the management framework, innovation results from selecting the right ideas and putting them to use in a way that makes them the value creator for the organization. Creativity is the development of original, distinctive ideas. Thus, combining creativity and innovation while considering the result is necessary, creating a platform with a stage for advancement and achievement.

Theodore Levitt, who claimed that "what is often lacking is not creativity in the idea-creating sense but innovation in the action-producing sense, i.e., putting ideas to work" (Levitt, 2002, p. 139), shared a similar perspective.

CREATIVITY

The individual, the process, the thing, and the context are the four distinct components that define creativity (Brown, 2013). This viewpoint focuses on the creative process that strengthens new ideas by influencing chances. The definition of creativity, according to Stein (1953; 2014), is "a process that results in a novel work that is accepted as useful, tenable, or satisfying by a significant group of people at some point in time" (Stein, 2014).

An innovative work should be valuable to a group of people at large, according to this commonly held explanation, despite the literature's diversity of perspectives and interpretations. Additionally, it incorporates a social element into genuine endeavors to produce something novel for originality, creativity, feasibility, and efficiency (Runco & Jaeger, 2012). Close observations by analysts (Shneiderman, 2007; Chen, 2006) revealed and characterized this process. As per Sternberg's (1999, p. 3) definition, creativity is the capability of producing work that is both appropriate (i.e., helpful, adaptable to task constraints) and unique (i.e., unusual, original).

The capacity for creativity is frequently noted as a trait some people possess while missing in others. However, the modern approach to managing creativity acknowledges that environments can improve the quality and reproducibility of creative endeavor and that everyone possesses fundamental abilities to produce creative work in their general environment. The three characteristics that Amabile identified as being associated exclusively with different or little-gathering creativity are inborn motivation to complete the task, aptitudes in the task area, and skills in creative reasoning (Amabile, 1988). The model there combines the elements of organizational passion and energy, management processes, and resources. It also includes the elements of aptitude and creativity capacities in individual and group creativity contexts. Amabile et al., 1996; Aslani et al., 2012) recognizes factors such as initiative, leadership, organization, administration, cooperation, participation, collaboration, teamwork, and organizational atmosphere as impacting factors.

The association between the managerial working environment and the imagination of individuals and gatherings was further viewed as people's creativity.

Since creativity is necessary before innovation and creative concepts are used for innovation, improving creativity in the workplace is crucial. Von Stamm (2008) portrayed it in the following discussions: "If the implementation is the act of putting an idea into practice, creativity is the act of having the idea in the first place. Creativity is a crucial component as the starting point for innovation (p. 2). In this way, creativity and imagination should be the foundation of innovation before moving on to creating the product, the strategy, the business model, the organizational practices, the related innovation, the applied technology, or the market.

INNOVATION

The study of innovation started many years ago (Marquis, 1969; Mansfield, 1968; Robertson, 1967) and developed in various ways and directions over time. The innovation approach and strategy are typically based on the four unique, interconnected measurements listed below.

Exploitation vs. Exploration: Exploitation strategy is focused on new items or capacities, expecting to provide another created item, process, or capacity, whereas exploration strategy is focused on existing organizational assets and abilities, intending to enhance, update, or upgrade efficiency (Shneiderman, 2007; Danneels, 2000; Benner & Tushman, 2003).

Technology push vs. market pull: Market pull is a process that starts with the identification of a need or a necessity for another good or a solution to a problem that comes from the market, then moves on to market research or market inquiry to look at potential outcomes, improvement generation, and sales. Technology push is a process that starts with research and development, continues with production, and then introduces the new product to the market. It typically begins when a company develops a new skill or innovation tied to another product and then advertises it to the public without market research (Stefano et al., 2012; Maital & Seshadri, 2012).

Internal vs. external capabilities: A company can adapt by combining its existing assets in new ways or by adding creative assets to identify its internal capabilities and crucial inner decisions. Examining the organizational value chain and identifying exercises that improve the assessment of the good or service for the market can improve the situation. Changes a corporation makes through exchanging essential capabilities are associated with external and externally important choices. These advancements can be made by hiring a resource or service from another company, collaborating with another company to trade assets, skills, or systems, or hiring an entire company with the necessary resources, skills, or methods (Von Stamm, 2008; Birkinshaw et al., 2008; Camisón & Villar-López, 2014; Cassiman & Veugelers, 2006).

Product vs. Process Innovation: Product innovation differs from process innovation in that it involves modifications to the specifications of a company's goods or services. These developments elevate the new goods or services above those the company now provides to its customers; they better account for their wants and preferences. Process innovation involves adjusting how a good or service is produced and delivered. Instead of the item or administration, these progressions are displayed in the creation or task forms (Brown, 2013; Adner & Levinthal, 2001).

The following options are the focus of many methodologies: 1) degree of innovation: incremental/radical; 2) stimulus for innovation: first mover/late mover; and (3) originality of the innovation: imitative/inventive (Gilbert, 1994; Germain, 1996; Afuah, 2003).

When a company adopts its innovation strategy, it should consider all these various aspects of innovation. However, the organization must lay the groundwork for the creative procedures after selecting the appropriate approach. Peter Drucker once said, "The entrepreneurial requires different management from the existing," in this vein. The entrepreneurial needs different management from the current. However, similar to the current, it needs to be managed in an ordered, systematic, organized, and purposeful manner (Drucker, 2014, p. 141). The following segment reviews a managerial point of view for managing innovation and leading creativity.

AN INTEGRATIVE FRAMEWORK FOR CREATIVITY AND INNOVATION

An effective organization needs both creativity and innovation if it wants to surpass expectations over the long term. Exercises in the following areas help creative organizations become more successful (Ireland et al., 2001). These areas include innovation, advancement, networks, systems, internationalization, organizational learning, hierarchical learning, top management teams and governance, top administration groups and administration, and development and growth. A comprehensive framework system suggests that while both management and leadership can achieve great quick results, only combining the two enables a continuous fruitful use, as evidenced by entrepreneurial behavior, successful and effective procedures, high-quality products, and exceptional business results. Although there is no doubt that management and leadership are related, developing creativity requires strong initiative and leadership that encourages staff to spot opportunities and come up with fresh concepts. If these ideas are handled scientifically to pick the ideas for implementation, accurately portray the chosen ideas, assess efficiency and effectiveness, and assist staff in further identifying opportunities, they will become crucial to the organization.

Organizational leaders create a domain portrayed with trust, interest, curiosity, resistance, and tolerance of variety after first identifying opportunities (Woodman et al., 1993; Amabile et al., 1996; Brattström et al., 2012). When this happens, the employee is constantly looking for more efficient ways to do tasks and to improve the process, the product, or the workplace.

According to Chemers (2014), leadership is "a procedure of social impact in which a man can enlist the guide and support of others in the achievement of a usual task." This gives the employee assurance, lack of fear, eagerness to implement an improvement, and the courage to take risks while developing new ideas. According to Gumusluoglu and Ilsev (2009) and Sosik et al. (1998), transformational leadership involves the followers, creates a shared vision to manage change through motivation, increases awareness of the magnitude of desired results and better methods to achieve those results, and implements changes with the group's designated members. The subsequent phase of selecting the ideas for use calls for organized, simple, and purposeful techniques that give every single employee an equal opportunity to have his or her idea carefully picked. The association of all employees in this method depends on an organized managerial practice. Another crucial factor that encourages people to be creative at work is the knowledge that their dedication will be appreciated through awards and recognition and by successfully implementing the chosen ideas. At this stage, competent and controlled actions are needed to carry out inventive and creative thoughts. The final step in the cycle of creativity and innovation at work refers to the continual process of change and improvement, which can be facilitated by top management support for ongoing, uninterrupted, ongoing, ongoing change procedures. Top managers act as facilitators (Cooper, 2003) and effectively communicate at operational and strategic levels (Everse, 2011).

This method, which addresses leadership for innovation and the administration of creativity, creates a continuous process that propels a company towards excellence, quality, and an entrepreneurial spirit.

Although the structure can be used in any institution, it is challenging in a contemporary organization. We are accustomed to seeing creative projects developed by ecstatic and risk-seeking supervisors and managers in the cutting-edge sector and R and D foundations. However, the workplace in contemporary organizations is characterized by a strong hierarchical structure in which essential methodologies are strictly followed to ensure the precise development of the stipulated item according to quality, usefulness, schedule, and cost. As a result, while it is generally much more complex, actualizing the coordinated structure of creativity and innovation in this situation is also significantly more rewarding.

THE IMPORTANCE OF LEADERS IN THE INNOVATIVE PROCESS

Research has shown that management tools such as organizational structure, strategy, technique, innovation, culture, and technology can give organizations a competitive advantage (Galbraith, 2002). They also show how creativity and innovation are the key sources of competitive advantage in the organizational context of the twenty-first century. However, these innovators need to mention more about the role of leadership in innovative practice. Companies that are innovative and compelling fail by accident. They anticipate that leaders will oversee significant adjustments to the organization's structure, culture, and procedures to transform them into creative, captivating, and profitable ones. Even though many organizations try to gain an advantage through their structure, technique, strategy, and culture, leadership is the most crucial source of advantage and competitive advantage. Organizational leaders typically decide what happens and provide the direction, vision, and zeal necessary to achieve goals. The environment, organizational culture, and processes that energize and manage development, sufficiency, and achievement in the organization are made and dealt with by leaders.

When an organization establishes its strategy and organizational structure, its executives direct the execution, which leads to success. Technique, strategy, the appropriate culture, and technology are crucial and help the organization succeed. However, for any of these crucial perspectives to truly benefit, the leadership must support, direct, energize, and inspire followers for it to succeed. Therefore, any organization must establish the appropriate leaders and hierarchical structures before the innovation process begins. In addition, the leaders themselves need to be innovative; else, they risk stifling creativity and innovation in the workplace. The finest organizational leaders typically have the ability and expertise to develop procedures that spur innovation; therefore, if these leaders cannot recognize opportunities for improvement, do not want to exploit them, or are unable to respond to them, they may stifle it. If the leaders' aims are energizing, aggressive, and creative and exhibit proactive attitudes and the capacity to respond to change, this may help the organization grow, recharge, and succeed.

According to certain management theorists, management instruments such as effective work forms, appealing strategy, and culture—not just leadership—determine managerial effectiveness (Cameron & Quinn, 1999). For instance, they use Japan's technology and automobile sector to show how their strong corporate culture contributed to their success. Further evidence of the importance of culture in organizational success comes from experimental studies (Denison, 1990). However, Schein has also shown that leaders are the ones who develop an organization's culture (Schein, 1985).

Organizations with weak leadership typically experience lower levels of success and are more likely to rebuild and scale back to address their problems constantly. On the other hand, organizations with creative and inventive leaders try to avoid the need for significant rebuilding and cutting back. These executives skillfully manage the company, preventing it from progressing to the point at which extensive restructuring is to be undertaken. According to statistics, many businesses that have adopted reengineering initiatives have failed because they needed more imaginative and creative leadership to handle the process.

This shows that management tools alone cannot ensure organizational creativity, which leads to innovation, development, sufficiency, effectiveness, success, and achievement. Businesses need creative, imaginative, compelling, innovative, and viable leadership to make the management tools function.

Even though most organizations can only accomplish their goals with strong leadership, many fail when providing leadership that inspires innovation, creativity, and success. According to Senge and Deming (1997), a significant portion of the problems and setbacks that organizations experience is caused by a lack of creative leadership. Since technique, strategy, technology, innovations, and advancements will only help an organization succeed with exemplary imaginative, creative, innovative, and effective leadership, leadership is the primary, foundational, and fundamental competitive advantage for progress. In order to cope with the application of the technique and foster innovation within the organization, organizations need creative and engaging leadership.

According to a study by Andersen Consulting, companies with creative leadership experienced a 900% increase in stock price over ten years, compared to only a 74% increase in companies without creative leadership (Agbor, 2008). Therefore, the ability of organizations to create a structure that fosters the development of new creative leaders to manage the organization is crucial (DuPont, 2002).

THE TYPE OF LEADERSHIP THAT ENCOURAGES INNOVATION

Companies' organizational structures for leadership support the delivery of outcomes that can foster creativity and innovation. In any event, only one unusual leadership approach can seize this opportunity. Interest in particular models and styles of leadership might result in creative outcomes.

Effective organizations have discovered that common, shared, and collaborative leadership unlocks an organization's potential, not brave and dictatorial management (Askenas et al., 2002). Employees in authoritarian, progressive, hierarchical, charge-control, command-and-control organizations must be more empowered, enabled, innovative, and productive (Hornstein & De Guerre, 2006). This is because the best leaders control these organizations' work, data, choices, and portions of assets. This type of approach emphasizes leadership as an expansion of the actions and intentions of the top leader. This historical leadership style was well-known in the eighteenth century and is still used in many organizations today (Harrison, 1999). In followers' perceptions of leaders, organizations describe the advanced version of this leadership strategy as people with the most noteworthy thoughts who produce amazing feats in the organization on their own. In these organizations, the leaders have clear objectives, and the followers believe they are ultimately responsible for every outcome and for ensuring that organizational processes are efficient.

This chivalrous approach to leadership has little chance of fostering growth and repair because leaders cannot build successful organizations on their own. Instead, leadership consists of individuals with various skills and tools who work together to transform the organization (Spillane, 2005). The ability to inspire, enable, and apply broad influence inside the organization constitutes elective leadership, as opposed to one person's capacity to take on responsibilities. Modern leaders know that no one has all the knowledge, skills, or time necessary to complete the complex tasks of modern leadership. They understand that since leadership positions are available at every level of the organizational hierarchy, organizations will not thrive if their leadership is limited to the top leaders. Therefore, for an organization to be creative and successful, it must capitalize on the creativity and innovation of its members. Organizations can do this by combining all of their leadership capabilities.

Everyone in the organization ought to be involved in its leadership in some way, according to Bergmann and Horst (1999).

According to Realin, organizations in the twenty-first century must be knowledge-based and need everyone to share the experience of acting as a leader; this entails sharing authority, responsibility, traits, and desires and working together to advance the organization (Realin, 2003). When this occurs, the organization eliminates the followers' oppressive reliance on the top leader, freeing them to contribute their skills to the organization. Tichy (1997) argues that instead of maintaining an order-and-control leadership structure, which frequently stifles creativity, many successful and creative organizations today draw from diverse sources of decisive leadership. Therefore, dispersing leadership and empowering and engaging everyone via preparation and training so they become innovative and creative leaders themselves is the best way to build an inventive, energetic, and compelling organization (Gardner, 2000).

HOW LEADERS ENCOURAGE CREATIVITY AND INNOVATION

Any organization that wants to foster creativity and innovation must recognize leaders' role in fostering these traits. By structuring the organization to foster an environment conducive to creativity, leaders may effectively encourage organizational creativity and innovation. Leaders can accomplish this by creating hospitable and thorough working environments for the organization's members. When professionals feel comfortable and appreciated in their roles, the organization's social structure fosters creativity (Pfeffer, 1998).

As a result, organizational leaders must acknowledge, value, and address each employee's diverse perspectives, thoughts, and backgrounds while also allowing them to apply their unique personal experiences and resources to their work (Meurling, 2004). Additionally, the most extraordinary organizational leadership must value creativity and be enthusiastic about supporting new developments. This provides the necessary test and creates opportunities for creativity among organization members (Kuhn, 1993). The organization's ability to effectively promote innovation and foster creativity depends on the leadership's vision and strategic objectives. Therefore, motivating vision aid in creating a workplace where everyone can participate fully and achieve professional and self-improvement in the pursuit of a shared vision. Here, the leader encourages the remaining members of the general population to unleash their creativity by developing a shared vision for the kind of company they should create. The leader inspires others by giving them a goal and a stronger sense of mission. This kind of work environment fosters innovation and creativity, and this kind of leadership influences followers to change over time into vital and creative leaders.

Additionally, leaders can be more persuasive in encouraging creativity by viewing organizations as dynamic structures that are brimming with the creative potential and advancement that the majority of the general population possesses. Leaders tap into this creative and innovative capacity to address and resolve organizational difficulties. Fundamentally, leaders must stop seeing the majority of the workforce in the organization as machines and start treating them as living beings who work in living frameworks rather than machines. This viewpoint enables leaders to create teams with followers capable of adapting, alert to changes in their circumstances, and capable of deliberate improvement (Wheatley, 2001). However, the point at which leaders invite everyone to participate in plans and create organizational processes and procedures is the primary way they might saddle this innovative soul. This means that to fully utilize the organization's intellect, invention, and creativity. The leaders must incorporate the complete structure.

Additionally, leaders may help their organizations achieve their goals by energizing innovation. They achieve this by putting personnel to the test and releasing them to provide straightforward solutions to problems. Leaders pose questions that encourage their followers to think freely. The motivating leader creates obstacles that encourage creative work in the organization. This type of leadership frees others and focuses their expertise, intelligence, creativity, and invention toward solving organizational problems and achieving organizational goals in fresh ways. According to Frank Sonnenberg and Beverly Goldberg (1992), organizational cultures that discourage creativity and innovation are the most challenging barrier to overcome for creative people.

This type of culture fosters the belief that the organization should consistently operate in the same manner as it did in the past. Such behavior is typically motivated by disappointment, office politics, and apprehension of anything novel or unusual. Creative leaders can recognize change, inspire followers to consider why the organization accomplishes its goals, and look for alternative ways to accomplish them. These leaders do not punish followers who try out novel ideas but fail because they see failure as a necessary part of the learning process. They contribute to the development of organizational cultures that allow people to take risks and even make mistakes.

The ability of an organization to innovate lies at its very heart. Accordingly, leaders should encourage creativity and innovation by creating environments more conducive to a healthy variety of ideas (Wren, 1996). To use followers' differences for a more effective operation of the organization, leaders must manage a variety of diversity. This suggests that managers must design the organizational social structures so that the majority of employees feel like they belong. They provide everyone in the organization a sense of value, stability, and recognition, which enables people to contribute much more of their talents and creativity to the business (Pfeffer, 1998). This suggests that the organizational leader recognizes, values, and uses the unique contrasts present in each individual (Weinzimmer, 2001). There are obstacles in many organizations that prevent people from giving all of their skills, ideas, and energies to the organization's success (Edwards, 1996). Organizations will, however, assume full responsibility and commitment from their entire staff when they recognize and remove barriers to diversity. Developing original ideas and creative solutions in workplaces with natural diversity becomes easier. According to Edwards, diverse viewpoints in the workforce fosters more innovation, creativity, problem-solving skills, adaptation, and flexibility (Edwards, 1996). When people with different backgrounds and abilities work together, they frequently bring fresh perspectives and challenge the organization's assumptions. Diversity, however, does not happen by accident. Alternatively, leaders of organizations should first be convinced of the benefits of diversity before persuading various members of the organization of its benefits. When this occurs, they will implement policies and procedures to ensure a reasonable amount of diversity inside the organization.

CONCLUSION

The relationship between innovation and company success is particularly significant in the current dynamic field. These days, it is common knowledge, and many organizations work to foster imagination, creativity, and innovation. In any event, there are a few challenges associated with implementing these principles in a modern organization because of the characteristics of this type of organization. The current study presents a historically significant, fruitful contextual investigation of implementing a creative and innovative culture in an organization. It illustrates how management and leadership are used to drive organizational transformation that will last over the long term and continue adding value to the organization.

We advise managers to establish a "Creative and Innovation Club" in contemporary organizations. It is crucial to create a stable work environment that rewards managers and employees for their creativity rather than criticizing them when they fall short. Additionally, it is crucial to establish a planned and uncomplicated infrastructure that will continue to back these operations and transform them from a one-time beneficial activity to a reasonable moving edge.

The most crucial aspect of organizational creativity and innovation is organizational leadership. Without the leaders putting the mechanism in motion and supporting it, no organization can reform or recover itself. In order to manage the innovation process, organizations need creative, innovative, and inventive executives. Therefore, an organization's originality depends on how the leader structures the organization and creates an environment that fosters creativity. It may also depend on how they promote and manage diversity inside the company. Lastly, it depends on how the leader inspires each person to tap into their best imagination, creativity, and innovation and use that to guide, transform, and improve the organization.

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